

NOTES

TABLE—1,2-DISUBSTITUTED ARYL-5,6,7,8-TETRAHYDRO-4-QUINAZOLINETHIONES

No.	R	R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	% Sulphur	
						Theoretical	Found
1.	H	H	127-28	54	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ S	10.1	9.4
*2.	H	OCH ₃	154-55	49	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS	9.2	8.8
3.	H	NO ₂	104	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	8.8	8.6
*4.	H	CH ₃	156-58	55	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ S	9.6	9.5
**5.	H	Br	115	51	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ SBr	8.1	7.6
6.	Br	H	97	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ SBr	8.1	7.7
7.	Br	NO ₂	90	48	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ SBr	7.3	6.9
8.	Br	CH ₃	103	48	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ SBr	7.8	7.4
9.	Br	Br	94	52	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ SBr ₂	6.7	6.5
10.	Br	Cl	75	48	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ SBrCl	7.4	7.0
**11.	Cl	H	87	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ SCl	9.1	8.7
**12.	Cl	OCH ₃	67	46	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ OSCl	8.4	8.4
13.	Cl	CH ₃	138	49	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ SCl	8.7	8.6
14.	Cl	Br	74	46	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ SBrCl	7.4	7.0
**15.	Cl	Cl	130-31	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ SCl ₂	8.3	8.0

* These compounds show mild antihistaminic activity compared to Mepyramine maleate.

** These compounds show weak antifungal activity compared to Grisofulvin.

the quinazolino thione, also available directly by three component systems discussed above.

In the present study, 1-morpholino-1-cyclohexene was condensed with benzoyl isothiocyanates and aryl amines in tetrahydrofuran. The products obtained were 1,2-disubstituted aryl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-quinazoline thiones, some of these were confirmed via the oxazine thione route. Some of these compounds showed very mild antifungal activities and antihistamine activity. Table describes the compounds prepared.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

Typical procedure for the synthesis is described below :

Benzoyl isothiocyanates were prepared by known methods. 1-Morpholino-1-cyclohexene was prepared according to Hunig *et al.*³

1-*o*-Methoxyphenyl-2-phenyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-4-quinazolinethione :

A mixture of 1-morpholino-1-cyclohexene (1.024 g; 0.006 mole), benzoyl isothiocyanate (1 g; 0.006 mole) and *c*-anisidine (1.511 g; 0.0123 mole) in tetrahydrofuran (10 ml) was refluxed on a boiling water bath for 4 hr. On cooling, the product obtained was filtered (crude melts at 148°-50°). It was recrystallized from tetrahydrofuran and melted at 154°-55°.

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Cyanoethylation of Sulphonamides

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MISRA *et al.*¹⁻³ and Shukla *et al.*⁴ in their earlier communications have reported the cyanoethylation of benzylphenyl sulphones, benzyl sulphonamides, benzene sulphonamides and *N*-substituted sulphonamides. Among them *p*-chlorobenzylphenyl sulphone was found to be very effective followed by the *o*-chlorobenzyl phenyl sulphone. All the compounds showed considerable toxicity to housefly (*Musca nebulosa*). These workers found that the introduction of cyanoethyl group increases the effectiveness of the drug.

Sulpha drugs have strong bacteriostatic properties. It was therefore, considered worthwhile to modify the structure of these compounds by superimposing the toxophoric group -CH₂CH₂CN on them and test for their insecticidal activity, in view of the excellent results achieved earlier.

Cyanoethylation of sulphanilamide and sulphapyridine was reported⁵ with acrylonitrile in dioxane solvent using sodium hydroxide as catalyst.

In the present communication, we have synthesized the cyanoethylated products of some more sulphonamides with acrylonitrile in dioxane solvent using benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide (Triton B) as catalyst with a view to finding out some more potential insecticides.

It is noticed that sulphanilamide when cyanoethylated in acetic acid medium, the active hydrogen atoms of the amido and *p*-amino groups were cyanoethylated.

TABLE I—CYANOETHYLATED SULPHONAMIDES

Srl. No.	Compounds	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Reqd. %		Found %	
					C	H	C	H
1.	N,N-bis-(2-cyanoethyl)-sulphanilamide	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	143–144 (Lit. 145) ⁵	60	—	—	—	—
2.	N,N-bis-(2-cyanoethyl)-acetyl-sulphanilamide	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ S	131 (Lit. 131–32) ⁵	60	—	—	—	—
3.	N-(2-cyanoethyl)-2-pyridyl-sulphanilamide	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	165 (Lit. 165) ⁵	70	—	—	—	—
4.	N-(2-cyanoethyl)-2-thiazolyl-sulphanilamide	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂	120–121	75	46.76	3.895	46.38	4.03
5.	N-(2-cyanoethyl)-2-pyrimidyl-sulphanilamide.	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₅ S	211–212	76	51.48	4.290	51.51	5.00
6.	N-(2-cyanoethyl)-4-methylpyrimidyl-sulphanilamide.	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₅ S	205–206	62	51.14	4.918	50.71	4.80
7.	N-(2-cyanoethyl)-4,6-dimethylpyrimidyl sulphanilamide.	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₅ S	171–172	68	54.39	5.136	54.81	5.15
8.	N,N,N',N'-tetracyanoethyl sulphanilamide.	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆ S	137–138	70	56.26	5.208	56.00	4.80
9.	N,N',N'-tricyanoethyl-2-pyridyl-sulphanilamide.	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆ S	151–152	69	58.08	5.135	59.05	5.50
10'	N,N',N'-tricyanoethyl-2-thiazolyl-sulphanilamide.	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	180–181	55	52.18	4.348	52.50	4.80

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

N,N-bis-(2-cyanoethyl)-sulphanilamide

To a well stirred solution of sulphanilamide (2 g.) and benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide (0.5 g.) in dioxane (15 ml.), was added acrylonitrile (1.3 g) dropwise at room temperature and refluxed for 1 hr. on a water bath. The reaction mixture was cooled, stirred for 48 hr. and neutralized with dilute hydrochloric acid. The white precipitate separated out was recrystallised from ethanol in colourless shining needles, m.p. 143°–144° (Lit. 145°)⁵. Yield: 2.0 g. (60% of theory).

N,N,N',N'-tetracyanoethyl sulphanilamide

Acrylonitrile (10.6 g.) was added slowly to sulphanilamide (8.6 g.) in glacial acetic acid (2 ml.). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 12 hr., cooled and poured on ice pieces. The white solid mass which separated was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate, recrystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 137°–138°. Yield: 13.5 g. (70% of theory). Found: C, 56.00; H, 4.80%. C₁₈H₂₀O₂N₆S required: C, 56.26; H, 5.21%.

The m.p., yield and analytical data for the sulphonamides are recorded in Table 1.

The compounds synthesized were tested for their insecticidal activity against *adult houseflies* and *Aedes larvae*. All the compounds were screened with contact-, stomach poison- and vapour phase methods. In the tests carried out, no insecticidal activity occurred anywhere.

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